

Adults watching numbers: Numerical information about COVID-19 presented in Greek TV news

Eleni Giannakopoulou, Hellenic Open University, ✉ giannakopoulou.eleni@ac.eap.gr

Since March 2020 a state of emergency has been imposed on the people in Greece, under which restrictions in their movements and lockdowns in the economic, social and cultural activities are from time to time imposed or removed, limited or extended by governmental decisions. These decisions are justified almost exclusively by numerical data: numbers of infections, people tested daily, deaths, hospitalized patients and patients in intensive care units and at the same time numbers of daily individual violations of restrictions. This paper reports on an analysis of numerical information about COVID-19 communicated by the prime-time news bulletins of two national TV channels on a daily basis over the previous year and we are claiming that once again numbers were used to manipulate citizens' views and attitudes.

Governing by numbers

Nowadays numbers constitute a crucial element of every political decision-making process and are used to proclaim the “rationality” of choices and “objectivity” of options, while at the same time conceal the political expediencies and the power relations involved.

The daily TV news bulletins and the front pages of newspapers are typical examples of the multiple uses of numbers in public discourse aiming to present an existing “reality”, on the basis of which governmental decisions or political actions seem to be “in fact inevitable”. On the other hand, however, it may be claimed that numbers and more broadly numerical expressions do not simply describe an existing reality, but also, they co-create a reality which then is portrayed as existing reality. The numerical expressions of particular aspects of political, social or economic facts involve implied choices which overvalue some of their features and devalue some others. In portraying this reality, the media frequently employs reasoning which may not be considered as neutral. In this way, the numerical expressions used create a “topos”, a mathematical term, which restricts our views of the respective aspects of political, social or economic life and determines our thinking and actions concerning issues related to these aspects. As was succinctly put by Rose (1991), “Numbers here delineate ‘fictive spaces’ for the operation of government, and establish a “plane of reality”, marked out by a grid of norms, on which government can operate” (p. 676).

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How do numerical expressions delineate “fictive spaces” in political activities? The answer, of course, is not, simple and exceeds the limits of this paper. However, we may outline in a few words some points of an answer inspired by Rose (1991).

First of all, the use of numbers is a key element in any process of transforming an economic, social or political issue into a problem that requires a solution by quantifying and expressing it numerically. In other words, the numerical description of an issue allows its formulation as being an economic, social or political problem and correspondingly the tackling of such a problem presupposes its statement in terms of numerical expressions between its selected characteristics.

Secondly, numerical expressions restrict any evaluation of political actions and particularly of governmental decisions. Hence, the success or failure of such decisions are dependant and expressed in quantitative changes and numerical correlations, which specify the achievement of goals, the fulfillment of declarations or the solution of problems, e.g., tackling unemployment.

Finally, numbers legitimize the exercise of power by certifying its representation to the people. For instance, the numerical expressions of public opinion polls express the correlations between governmental actions and orders of the people whose name power is exercised in.

The effectiveness of the above functions of numbers in politics is mostly grounded on the hegemony of numerical discourse in modern societies which provides apparent objectivity and legitimacy in numerical expressions as has been analyzed by Sfard (2009).

There is no doubt that the relationships between numerical expressions and political actions are much more complex than the ones outlined in a simplistic way above and they have been the subject of analyses from various viewpoints and approaches as we may see by the relevant literature (e.g., Bartl al. 2019; Chassapis & Giannakopoulou, 2015; Demortain, 2019; Fioramonti, 2014; Gilles 2016; Shore & Wright, 2015; Skovsmose 2010).

In this paper, the issue of using numbers by governments to manipulate citizens’ views and attitudes is put as a preliminary note related to the politics concerning the pandemic, an aspect of which will be analyzed below.

The numbers of COVID-19 pandemic in Greek TV channels

The first cases of COVID-19 were confirmed in Greece at the end of February 2020, and since then a state of emergency has been imposed on the people. Under this state of emergency, restrictions on movements and lockdowns in the economic, social and cultural activities of the people were from time to time imposed or removed, limited or extended by government. All these restrictions were justified almost exclusively by numerical data. A daily briefing was introduced by government during which health officials and experts presented the current situation of the pandemic using, almost exclusively, numerical data. Such data consists of numbers of new cases of infection, of people tested and those found positive, as well as of deaths, numbers of people hospitalized, and of patients in intensive care units. In addition, various numerical indices also are included, such as the virus reproduction index

or virus risk degree. All these numbers are daily calculated and cumulative over various time periods. At the same time government announced numbers of daily violations of individual movements and activity restrictions. These briefings lasted about an hour and were being broadcasted live on all national television networks. The numerical information announced by officials and experts, was enriched with visual representations (graphics, diagrams, tables etc.) and supplemented with journalistic comments reproduced by TV channels in their main evening newscasts, where they usually have their maximum audience.

After a short lifting of restrictions during the summer all restrictions on people and activities were re-applied in October 2020. However, in this second wave of the pandemic, the role of informing the public was entirely assigned by the government to the TV channels. Since then, the prime-time TV news has started with a bombardment of numerical information about COVID-19 followed by a variety of interpretations provided by journalists, health experts and politicians, most of them supporting relevant governmental decisions which were sometimes hardly justifiable. Under the conditions created in the country by the restrictions on individual movements and the suspension of all labour, economic and social activities, the TV broadcasts became, for a majority of people, the main source of information about the pandemic. In this way, TV channels turned into a powerful instrument influencing the perceptions and shaping the social reality of the viewers by selecting, framing and transmitting numerical information about COVID-19, thus creating a meaning about the pandemic.

The governmental management of the pandemic, as evidenced by its decisions and proclamations, was based on two political strategies. The first one was the production and dissemination of a storm of numerical information which day by day shaped the image of citizens about pandemic and its dangers emphasizing above all their individual responsibilities in preventing virus spread. The second strategy was the mobilization and assignment of a primary role on TV news bulletins and broadcasts in tackling pandemic. On this ground, the government funded TV networks with special grants on the pretext of informing citizens. It is almost certain that no other event in recent Greek history has been covered to such an extent and duration by the media with such a flood of numerical information.

This paper reports on findings of an analysis of numerical information about COVID-19 which was communicated by the prime-time news of two national TV channels on a daily basis over the previous year.

The guiding theoretical perspective of our analysis stems from framing theory (Goffman, 1974). The basis of framing theory is that the media attracts attention on certain events and then places them within a field of meaning. In essence, framing theory suggests that the way in which something is presented to the audience (called “the frame”) influences the choices people make. Framing can support the investigation of media influence on the audience, by seeking to outline different patterns of presentation of the news broadcasted by them. According to this sociological approach, frames stand as the mechanism for perceiving complexity of the surrounding world in a simplified way and numerical depiction seems to

be a very effective instrument for highlighting significant information and putting aside unnecessary details. As put by Entman (1993, p. 53),

to frame is to select some aspects of a perceived reality and make them more salient in a communicating text, in such a way as to promote a particular problem definition, causal interpretation, moral evaluation, and/or treatment recommendation for the item described.

To sum up, the structures of TV news bulletins (media frames) offer to their audience aspects of perceived reality so as specific interpretations, attributions or evaluations are suggested.

The numerical fluency of Greek adult TV audience

The numerical storming of TV channels was being addressed to an adult audience ignoring the only available nationwide research, the “Survey of Adult Skills”. It was, carried out during 2014–2015 by the PIAAC-Programme for the International Assessment of Adult Competencies (OECD, 2016) which identified the low level of numeracy in the populace. In this survey numeracy is defined as the ability of adults to use numerical and mathematical concepts. The PIAAC survey found that the share of adults in Greece who score at the highest levels of proficiency in numeracy is considerably smaller than the OECD average (252 in Greece while 263 is the OECD average on a scale of 500 points). More specifically, about 6% of adults in Greece attain the higher levels in numeracy (OECD average 11%) and about 25% of adults attain the middle level (OECD average 32%). At the middle level, adults have a good sense of number and space, can recognize and work with mathematical relationships, patterns and proportions expressed in verbal or numerical form, and can interpret and perform basic analyses of data and statistics in texts, tables and graphs. On the other hand, the proportion of adults with poor numeracy skills is much larger in Greece than OECD average. Almost 28.5% of Greek adults score at the low level of numeracy (OECD average is about 23%). Some 27% of 16–24-years-olds are low performers in numeracy (OECD average 19%). Low proficiency is also prevalent among 55–65-year-olds in Greece: about one in three adults at this age group score at the low level in numeracy. Adults at the low numeracy level can perform basic mathematical processes in common, concrete contexts, for example, one-step or simple processes involving counting, sorting, basic arithmetic operations and understanding simple percentages. In relation to the educational level of adults it is interesting to note the finding that tertiary-educated adults in Greece have relatively low proficiency in numeracy (OECD 2016). Although we have to be skeptical when reading international survey reports (Evans, 2014), this is a picture of the adult numeracy situation in Greece as outlined by PIAAC findings and addressing such an audience TV channels broadcast every day a storm of numerical information.

Research methodology

This paper reports on an analysis of numerical information about COVID-19 communicated by selected news bulletins of two national TV channels. The two channels were selected on

the basis of their character (a public ERT1 and a private Skai) and their nationwide spectatorship. From all their everyday evening news bulletins were broadcasted from February 17, 2020 (when the first cases of COVID-19 confirmed) until October 4, 2020 (when a strict lockdown was imposed once again in the country), a convenience sample was selected. The main selection criterion was to have been broadcasted on dates when restrictions were imposed or removed, limited or extended by government decisions. So, it was analyzed 112 evening news broadcasted by the two TV channels in which the pandemic was their first issue covered mostly by numerical information and its interpretation lasting from 15 to 35 minutes. The TV news were analyzed by applying a variation of the content analysis (Neuendorf, 2017). As it is known, content analysis is a research tool used to determine the presence of certain concepts, within any occurrence of communicative language. Under the scope of our research, it is numbers and numerical expressions that are the organizing concept of our content analysis.

The main findings of this analysis are briefly presented in the following sections.

The choice of numbers

The TV news programs organize their reports around numbers. Although the information provided may sound real to the audience, its meaning is not clear for many reasons. According to our evidence, the news broadcasts are focused mostly on raw numbers or percentages without reference to unit populations. Graphics as in the following two examples were typical at the start of the news. Figure 1 shows the original TV screen while the next one is translated by the author. The presenters comment on the new confirmed cases (1678 cases) and the numbers of cases in one city and three regions of the country in which large numbers of infected people were detected. The caption “informs” the audience that “positivity is over 10%” without any explanation of the meaning of “positivity”.

Figure 1: Raw numbers introducing pandemic situation one day on Skai TV (Skai TV, News bulletin on November 1, 2020, 19:50 o'clock local time).

Figure 2 presents a sequence of raw numbers reporting daily infected cases over the first month of the pandemic as well as their total (892 cases).

None of the numbers shown in these particular screenshots, and nor on all the TV news are standardized. Thus, without any reference to the population sizes, it is completely unclear

to what extent the numbers of cases depend on the relative sizes of the populations referred to. Nonetheless, the use of numbers conveys the information and comments on a sense of objectivity. As Porter (1995) puts it, the language of mathematics is well suited to embody objective judgments and it is adopted when claims to knowledge are needed to gain trust and credibility beyond the bounds of locality and society.

Figure 2: A sequence of raw numbers reporting the evolution of pandemic during the first month of pandemic on ERT1 TV (ERT1 TV, News bulletin on March 26, 2020, 21:00 o’clock local time).

Although seemingly extreme, it may be claimed that raw numbers displayed on TV screens highlight the individuality of cases by removing from the counts their frames of reference which are their social context, thus isolating the cases of infected, hospitalized or deaths and delete any sense of belonging. Everyone is alone in the pandemic and this is one of the “lessons” promoted by TV channels. Therefore, individual responsibility and not social policies is the weapon against the pandemic.

Beyond integers the second prevalent numerical expression in communications about COVID-19 are percentages denoting either indices, for instance the virus reproduction index, or parts of a whole which was usually not explicit. Whilst percentages are a seemingly simple numerical concept, it is known that they confuse and disorientate people. Here its use implies more than it displays, since it does not denote a quantity but a relation between two quantities; actually, it is a fraction whose denominator is 100 and thus the expression of increase or decrease of a quantity is not always easily conceived. Expressing a relation between two quantities, the value of a percentage is dependent on the change of the one or the other quantity or both. At the same time, when it is displayed and commented on, even when compared the one percentage or the another as a single numeral, these quantities are not referred to, at all. Since percentages are numerical expressions representing a ratio, not just a quantity, being displayed as single numbers, they become suitable for numerical alchemies and appropriate for manipulations projecting a false or a distorted picture of a reality.

In Figure 3 percentages and decimals are employed to display the hazards of the pandemic on a particular day using terms which may be unknown to the majority of the audience: positivity index 8.3%, alarm limit 4%, Rt (reproduction rate) 0,68 in Athens, 0,85 in Thessaloniki.

Finally, the third type of numerical expression which was mostly included in TV describes various aspects of the pandemic based decimal numbers. Decimals are rational numbers but

their writing refers, at first sight, to counting numbers and since each decimal number displays the “part” obscuring the “whole” to which it refers (its denominator), its comprehension often difficult.

Figure 3: Percentages and decimals describing hazards of pandemic on Skai TV (Skai TV, News bulletin on November 1, 2020, 19:50 o’clock local time).

As portrayed by our analysis, the decimal numbers broadcasted on TV news are rather perplexing than informative. As shown in Figure 3, the decimal numbers express rather incomprehensible concepts to the majority of audience, as is virus reproduction rate ($R_t=0.68$). In Figure 4, decimal numbers present discrete quantities as if they were continuous, as is the number of 0.625 people infected by one person. In the same screen the merits of individual self-restraint in dealing with the pandemic are exposed with the following implicit numerical argument: if self-restraint by a person is 75% (sic), then that person in 5 days will infect 0.625 persons and in 30 days 2.5 persons. A personal self-restraint by 75%, as explained by presenter, means that a person has to reduce his/her social contacts by that percentage. How could one do that? In any case, the question of how this percentage is calculated remains without an answer.

Figure 4: Decimals describing the merits of individual self-restraint on ERT1 TV (ERT1 TV, News bulletin on March 19, 2020, 21:00 o’clock local time).

Numbers embedded in charts and diagrams

In many broadcasts, numbers as numerical sequences of infections, deaths, hospitalizations or recovering were used to depict the development of the pandemic in comparison to restriction measures imposed by government. Figure 5 is a typical example.

Figure 5: Number of deaths in total since the onset of the pandemic on ERT1 TV (ERT1 TV, News bulletin on November 5, 2020, 12:00 o’clock local time).

Numerical sequences are almost impossible to be comprehended and interpreted by the majority of the audience, given the situation of adult numeracy in Greece outlined previously. Thus, numbers concerning development of numerically expressed aspects of the pandemic were, in my view, included in charts and diagrams of TV shows in order to assign validity to comments of the presenters or justifications to governmental decisions rather than inform the audience.

Framing the interpretations of numbers

The comments of TV presenters and the interpretations offered by health experts, were made with references to the displayed on-screen numbers. These numbers, however, being row or relational numbers, as percentages or decimals, acquired their specific meaning by their, not explicit, but implied referents. Mostly however, the numbers acquired particular conceptions of their values by the quantitative expressions used by the presenters and commentators. For example, “numbers show an alarming exponential growth of infections”, “numbers reveal a significant, rapid and dangerous transmission rate”, “numbers may not seem big but they have great importance” etc.

At the same time, a variety of visual displays added an elaborate visual dimension to the numerical expressions which, without a doubt, influenced the interpretation of the audience. It is commonly assumed that visually presented numerical data, known nowadays, as infographics, convey information which can quickly be consumed and easily understood by an adult audience and for this reason they were extensively used by TV news in broadcasts about the COVID-19. However, the visual displays that the TV news bulletins utilized highlighting the numbers, create a referential field which, as Potter et al (1991, p. 343) has put, function as “parallel commentaries” which reinforce numerical expressions.

Concluding comments

As outlined in our theoretical framework, numbers serve political projects and government decisions. Firstly, by defining problems and delimiting their solutions by quantifying and expressing it numerically. Secondly, as a consequence, restricting the evaluations of related political actions and particularly of governmental decisions, and thirdly, legitimizing the

power exercised of by political authorities. The data presented in previous sections showed that TV news about COVID-19 was structured, throughout the period reviewed, around numerical expressions, enriched with visual representations and all framed by journalistic comments and health experts' interpretations. The particular numerical expressions used in these communications created particular images of the pandemic and its risks thus indirectly specifying the proper measures to deal with it or in other words defining the problems created by pandemic and predicting their solutions. The use of some specific types of numbers rather than others by TV news, the utilisation of certain mathematical ideas and the discourse surrounding them were value-laden supporting political purposes.

Given the low levels of adult numeracy in the country, as shown by the mentioned PIAAC survey, we can reasonably assume that for sizeable shares of TV audience the numbers as presented and commented on TV, may generate confusion or misunderstandings about many aspects of pandemic rather than informing on the actual risks and the appropriate actions, both individual and collective.

On the ground of such confusions, the numerical discourse which frames the numbers presented on TV created to the audience feelings of fear and through an individuation of numbers and facts promoted a sense of individual blaming for the current picture of the pandemic and its evolution concealing at the same time any governmental responsibilities. From the first days of the pandemic onwards the governmental officials, on their TV appearances, made individuals jointly liable for the spread of pandemic and for the failure of measures to tackle it. After all, the numerical communications employed by TV restricted the evaluations of related political actions and legitimized the governmental decisions.

Public opinion polls of those days reflect many aspects of the above conclusions. People were confused about crucial aspects of pandemic, possessed by feelings of fear and insecurity and the management of pandemic by numbers seemed rather successful, since the majority of people questioned evaluated the government decisions as effective (e.g., Eurobarometer, 2020; diaNEOsis, 2020).

Beyond conclusions, our findings raise many questions whose answers, however, require further research. Questions related to the impact that the particular use of numbers about the pandemic had on people's attitudes, legitimating the choices made by political authorities and finally, on enabling the tackling of the pandemic.

So, what may be a strategic response from the viewpoint of critical mathematics education? I would suggest promoting adult critical numeracy and the "reading" of COVID-19 numbers from such a perspective and of course, the publicity of this "reading". It is accepted that critical numeracy incorporates the abundant ways by which number concepts and facts are used by various agents for promoting their agendas. In addition, the social practices involved in each of these uses, the effects on power relationships generated through processes of number uses and overall aims to an understanding their consequences for individuals and societies (Geiger et al., 2015).

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